

IMPROVEMENT OF DETECTION OF DEFECTS OF CONCRETE IN THE INFRARED PULSE PHASE THERMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Pulse phase thermography (PPT) is one of the infrared thermography techniques which has some advantages over the conventional pulse thermography (PT): The PPT can detect deeper defects than the PT, and reduces effect of non-uniform heating. In this study, in order to further improve the defect detectability of the PPT, we tried to reduce noises appears on temperature and phase data using various image filters. We obtained higher-quality temperature images by minimizing the noise using a moving average filter, and showed that deeper defects was detectable in phase images by reducing the temperature noises. In addition, we tried to detect defect in the concrete structures using PPT with the heating by lamp. As a result, it was suggested that it is possible to detect a concrete internal defects in the heating using the developed halogen lamp.

1 INTRODUCTION

Infrared thermography is one of attractive non-destructive testing (NDT) methods because it is non-contact testing method and inspects large area in shorter time than other techniques such as radiography or ultrasonic methods. In the infrared thermographic methods, pulse thermography (PT) is frequently used method. In the PT, a surface of test object is heated instantaneously by flash lamps, and the surface temperature distribution after heating is monitored by an infrared camera. In temperature image thus obtained, subsurface defects appear as local hot or low areas, because the heat flow loaded from the surface is disturbed by the defects. However, It was reported that the infrared thermography can detect defects located within a few millimeter depth from the surface in carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), for which easier NDT is highly demanded in automotive and aircraft industries in recent years ^[1-3].

One of the techniques for improving the detectable defect depth is application of pulse phase thermography (PPT). In the PPT, temperature distribution as a function of time obtained by the PT is transformed into phase by the Fourier transform, and phase images are constructed from it^[4]. The PPT is able to apply to concrete [5], PMMA[6-7] and Aluminum structures [8], and to detect deeper defects than PT.

One of the conceivable ideas for more improving detectable depth of defects in PPT is reducing noises appears in the temperature data. In this study, in order to achieve high-quality temperature image, we tried to minimize noises by the using moving average filter. Then, improvement of the defect detectability in the phase images obtained from the noise-reduced temperature images were investigated.

Efficient damage assessment methods have been sought as aging measures of large civil engineering structures such as tunnels and bridges. In the conventional inspection is mainly utilized slapping sound, but on the method to a longer working time test, also a problem with cost increase scaffold installation, etc. for inspection. In this study, a concrete bridge as a target, along with the development of the long-distance heating device capable of heating the 20m destination of concrete, and tried to establish a long-range infrared non-destructive inspection method using an infrared camera with PPT method.

First, using infrared thermography to verify that it is possible to detect internal defects in the concrete, we examined the validity of the non-destructive inspection technique.

2 Pulse Phase thermography

A PPT inspection procedure is presented in Fig.1. Similarly to the PT method, a test object surface is heated by flash lamps. Then, the surface temperature is monitored using an infrared camera after heating ($T(t)$). Next, the discrete Fourier transformation is applied to $T(t)$ leading to phase as a function of frequency $\varphi(f)$ using following equation;

$$\varphi(f) = \tan^{-1} \frac{I(f)}{R(f)} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Therein, f stands for the frequency, and $R(f)$ and $I(f)$ are real and imaginary components obtained after the Fourier transform. In phase images, subsurface defects are detected by observing the phase difference between defective and sound surfaces ($\Delta\phi$).

Fig.1 Inspection and data processing procedure in the pulse phase thermography (PPT).

3 Noise on temperatures

Fig.2 (a) shows temperature noise obtained by an infrared camera used in this study by measuring the surface of a CFRP specimen under constant temperature. The sampling rate of the data was 15Hz, and data points were 4096. The solid curve in Fig.2 (b) is a histogram of the temperature noise amplitudes, wherein the dashed curve represents the normal distribution with standard deviation of 0.04° C. Fig.2 (c) shows the power spectrum of the temperature noise.

Fig.3 (b) shows analytically calculated temperature data obtained from a finite element analysis

using an axisymmetric model as seen in Fig3 (a). In the calculation, an instantaneous thermal load (square pulse with time duration of 3 ms) is applied to the upper surface. The outside temperature was assumed to be 20°C, and the respective heat transfer coefficient and radiation factor on both upper and lower surface were 10 [W/(m² K)] and 0.9. Thermal conductivity of out-of-plane and in-plane were 2 and 0.48 [W/(m K)] which assumed CFRP. Sampling rate and data points was 2Hz and 4096. In Fig.3 (b), calculated temperature data with white noise is also represented, and both the data with and without noise are transformed to phase data by Fourier transform as shown in Fig.3 (c). It is found from these figures that the noise appears in the temperature data causes correspondent noise in the phase data. In other words, these results suggest that minimization of noise in the temperature data should improve the defects detectability in the phase images.

Fig.2 (a) Temperature noise obtained using an infrared camera. (sampling rate: 15Hz, data points: 4096) (b) Comparison between the histogram of experimentally obtained temperature noise amplitude and a normal distribution curve (standard deviation: $\sigma = 0.04^{\circ}\text{C}$). (c) Power spectrum of temperature noise.

Fig.3 (a) Axisymmetric model used in FEM analysis. (b) Temperature data obtained by finite element method along with a white noise. (c) Phase data obtained by transforming (b).

4. Experiment

4.1 Test for detecting defects inside the concrete samples

The concrete sample with false defect shown in Fig.4 was used as detecting defects test. In figure, D means the depth of defect from heated surface. Specimen having a defect depth of 30mm and 50mm were used in this study.

Halogen Lamp (input power 1.0kw) in Fig.5 was used to heat the surface on concrete sample, heating time was 60s. The infrared camera (SC4000; FLIR systems Inc.) was equipped with 320×256 Indium Antimonide sensors (detectable wavelength region: 3~5 μ m), sampling rate was 1Hz.

Fig.4 Schematic view of concrete sample.

Fig.5 Configuration of test using a concrete test sample.

4.2 Heating characteristics and heating distribution measurement

Three types of lamp shown in Figure 6 were selected for heating the concrete. The difference of Type A and Type B is heating source. The difference of heating source influences the heating efficiency. On the other hand, Type B and Type C were prepared to confirm the difference in the focusing characteristics. It was subjected to measurement of the heat distribution that occurs on the board with these lamps in the test method shown in Fig7. As the test conditions, heating distance L was 1m and 15m, and the heating time was set to 120 seconds.

	Lamp type A	Lampe type B	Lampe type C
Heating source	Xenon lamp	Halogen lamp	Halogen lamp
Condensing method	Parabolic mirror	Parabolic mirror	Elliptic paraboloid mirror Fresnel lens
Input power (W)	1000	1000	450

Fig. 6 Details of heating lamp for heating characteristics and heating distribution measurement.

Fig.7 Test configuration of heating characteristics and heating distribution measurement.

5. Results

5.1 Test for detecting defects inside the concrete samples

Temperature images of concrete sample after heating are shown in Fig.8. In the figure, (a) is the sample depth of the defect is 30mm, (b) is a sample of 50mm depth of the defect. The defect penetrates through the sample in the vertical direction as shown in the Fig. 8, it was shown that the detection of the depth of defects of 50mm is possible only in the thermal image. On the other hand, the case of a defect penetrates through the sample in parallel direction as shown in Fig9, defects of 30mm depth at verification by temperature image has been detected, a defect of 50mm depth were detected. This is presumed to it due to the difference in heat transfer due to defects shapes. Therefore, PPT described above was performed to improve the detection accuracy. Fig. 10 shows the PPT image. From this figure, it has been shown to be capable of sensing the depth of the defect 50mm by PPT. It was shown that it is possible to detect internal defects in the concrete by utilizing the thermal image and the image PPT.

Fig.8 Temperature images of concrete sample.
((a)D=30, (b)D=50, defect penetrates through the sample in vertical direction)

Fig. 9 Temperature images of concrete sample.
((a)D=30, (b)D=50, defect penetrates through the sample in parallel direction)

Fig. 10 Phase image of concrete sample with 50mm depth defect. (PPT)

5.2 Heating characteristics and heating distribution measurement

Temperature images obtained in the tests carried out under the conditions of 1m heating distance is shown in Fig.11 and 12. As a result, it showed the heating by the halogen lamp is high heating characteristics. When using the device Type B, the heating unevenness was observed compared with the case of using the device Type C. This factor it considered to be affected by the filament shape.

That influence the shape of the filament is given to the heating distribution is large has been confirmed in the heating of at close range.

Figure.13 shows temperature image of heating test under condition of 15m heating distance. The heating by Type A lamp, local temperature rise only not observed, it was confirmed that no possible overall heating. The other hand, it is a heating test by the halogen lamp has occurred extensively relatively uniform heating was confirmed. This efficacy of the halogen lamp has been suggested from this result. In heating using the Type C, it shows a more uniform temperature distribution compared to use Type B. It is also estimated to remain the influence of the shape of the filament in this condition. However, the heating characteristics it obtained by the Type B has been shown to be excellent. This is considered as something due the influence of light absorption by Fresnel lens used for Type C. It is considered that it is necessary to determine the lamp to be used, in the consideration from both uniformity and heat characteristics.

Fig.11 2D and 3D Thermal image. (Heating distance is 1m)
((a) is Type A, (b) is Type B, (c) is Type C)

Fig.12 Temperature graph and the contour line in the thermal image . (Heating distance is 1m)
((a) is Type A, (b) is Type B, (c) is Type C)

Fig.13 Temperature graph and the contour line in the thermal image . (Heating distance is 15m)
 ((a) is Type A, (b) is Type B, (c) is Type C)

9 CONCLUSIONS

The test of detecting defects inside the concrete samples and Heating characteristics and heating distribution measurement, the following summary was obtained

It was shown that the detection of the depth of defects of 50mm is possible only in the thermal image in the defect penetrates through the concrete sample in the vertical direction

It has been shown to be capable of sensing the depth of the defect 50mm by PPT, Even under conditions where it is not confirmed by the thermal image.

Halogen lamp is high heating characteristics compared with xenon lamp to heat in the test condition in this study. Moreover, even when using the same heating method, it leaves a difference in temperature distribution and the heating characteristics are confirmed by the properties of the mirrors and lenses.

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